

Data Protection: Factors Influencing Retention and Destruction of Personal Information

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Abstract. Data privacy and protection of information is an important issue for consumers. The concerns that consumers have around the protection of their personal data has heightened due to the occurrence of cyber threats and organisations have an increasing need to implement effective data protection practices which includes securing and disposal of data. An integral part of the data life cycle refers to the destruction of data when it is no longer needed. This means that data must only be retained for the purpose of its collection. It is important to obtain reliable data to ensure proper security and protection. Privacy is the right to protection against unwanted collection and use of personal information. An organisations privacy data should be promptly disposed of at the end of the data retention period, unless stipulated otherwise by additional laws and regulations. To achieve effective destruction methods, efficient retention practices must be in place. The objective of this research is to present a framework to assist organisations in making decisions related to the timely and efficient destruction of data.

Keywords: Data Protection, Personal Information, Data Privacy, Data Retention, Data Destruction, Data Lifecycle, Data Classification.

1 Introduction

Since the advent of the digital era, the excessive use of digital media has inevitably led to the creation of extensive digital footprints. The digital footprints that are created often contain sensitive personal information, including individual preferences, consumer behaviours, private communication and cherished memories [1]. The global proliferation of internet connectivity and smart devices has further accelerated the continuous and large-scale generation of such data.

Consequently, organisations bear a significant responsibility to ensure effective information privacy protection. Privacy protection requires a multifaceted approach by incorporating regulatory compliance, advanced technological safeguards and industry best practices [1]. For data and information to be considered valuable, they must first be collected, captured, created, or generated [2]. Personal Information must be collected lawfully for a clearly defined purpose and must be adequately protected to prevent exploitation. Failure to comply with these principles may result in significant

penalties for the responsible entity [3]. Personal information (PI) is any piece of data that can be used to identify a living person or to ascertain their physical presence [4].

At every stage of the data lifecycle, organisations must be mindful of data protection [5]. The increasingly extensive collection of personal data has exacerbated concerns regarding the privacy and security of such information [6]. When data has reached the end of their lifecycle, a decision must be made about its destruction, as depicted in Fig. 1 under the destroy caption.

Fig. 1. Detailed breakdown of the phases of data lifecycle management adapted from Data Lifecycle Management [2] redrawn.

As illustrated in Fig. 1, at the final stage of the data life cycle, a decision must be made about its destruction [2]. Every stage of the life cycle introduces challenges in data security and reliability, underscoring the importance of protecting PII as a critical objective [7]. An organisation should regularly review its holdings of previously collected PII to determine whether the information is still relevant and necessary for meeting the organisation’s business purpose and mission [8]. Data and information which are no longer used and are not subjected to retention conditions should enter the destruction phase of the data lifecycle. Certain policies require companies to eliminate business records, either after a certain period has elapsed, upon contract termination, or simply when the data becomes obsolete [9].

Organisations are obligated to delete personal data unless mandated by law and must stop storing digitised data when it no longer serves its purpose or when users withdraw their consent [4]. The personal information record must be disposed of within a reasonable timeframe. Personal data must be unidentifiable, so the data subject is no longer identified and privacy is preserved [10]. The aim of this paper is to identify the factors that influence data retention and destruction and to propose an effective model that includes a framework with recommendations for organisations. The article will highlight the factors shaping the retention and destruction of personal information and will outline indicators for its effective management.

1.1 Background

Security and privacy preservation are critical concerns including the risk of unauthorised data breaches or information leaks that can result in financial losses [11]. If the risk of retaining nonregulated and/or nonlitigation-related data is more significant than its value, then that data should be considered for deletion [12][13]. Data must be scheduled for deletion if the risks of retention of the identified data outweigh its value. There must be a reliable solution to prove that data is deleted to prevent data leakage or abuse [14]. To prevent data from being leaked or abused, there is a need for a reliable and secure data deletion scheme to ensure that data owners can permanently delete valuable or sensitive data [15]. The extended retention times and decision to not delete data therefore increase the cost to store the data, while the data itself becomes less valuable the longer it is retained. A negative value-to-cost ratio highlights another reason to dispose of data [16].

Data holds immediate value at the point of its creation or collection, as it is actively utilised and assigned significance within organisational processes. Over time, as the data is processed and applied, it continues to retain value [16]. During the archival or storage phase of the data lifecycle, the organisational utility of data progressively diminishes. When data is retained for prolonged periods without active utilisation, its value declines markedly while the cost associated with its maintenance increases. This pattern highlights the necessity of implementing strategic data lifecycle management practices to optimise the balance between value preservation and cost efficiency [16].

1.2 Overview of data protection laws in the South African context

For organisations to ensure privacy and protection of the data they collect, process, use, store, share, archive, and destroy, various regulatory and legislative bodies have been put in place to enforce and oversee data protection compliance [13]. For example, the Information Regulator in South Africa, The European Data Protection Board in the United Kingdom, and the Central Consumer Protection Authority in the United States of America are regulatory authorities who advocate for the rights of the data subjects [17][18][19]. A significant number of authorities and data protection acts exist across the globe; however, the research focused on the South African context only and will refer to POPI and GDPR throughout the study [20][21].

The Protection of Personal Information Act in South Africa states that organisations should promptly dispose of or de-identify a personal information (PI) record [20]. The PI record must be disposed of within a reasonable timeframe when the organisation is no longer authorised to keep the record [20][22]. De-identification in terms of POPIA is a process whereby an organisation takes steps to delete all personal information that can identify a data subject in the data set and this practice forms part of the destruction process [22].

2 Research Method

The systematic review was conducted following the preferred reporting item for systematic review and meta-analysis (PRISMA) approach [23]. The PRISMA flow diagram in Fig.2 depicts the identification of records, screening records for relevance and then deciding which articles to include. Methods and results of the systematic reviews are illustrated in the search results under section 3. The literature review covered data retention and destruction and data protection practices that should be used.

Fig. 2. The information flow in the data protection and destruction systemic review is based on the PRISMA 2020 flow diagram [23].

Fig.2 Indicates this is a qualitative approach and non-human ethical clearance has been obtained for the study.

3 Search Results

Keyword searches were used for searching academic databases. The search was carried out by applying a standardised search string consistently across all databases and articles. The search criteria were systematically modified to conform to the indexing conventions of each library, thereby ensuring compatibility. During the systematic literature review, the databases searched were ScienceDirect, Web of Science, Sabinet, and

Google Scholar, with no registers used. Other methods used include website searches and conference proceedings. The following keywords were used in the search string:

“data destruction” “data protection” “methods” “data classification” “retention” AND “data privacy”

The use of this search string returned results of articles related to data retention and methods of destruction but also included retention not relating to data in the technology field. The same keyword search was used to only include articles from computer science and technology journals. Ensuring completeness in the collection of search results obtained backward and forward searching was conducted.

Additional search criterion was used in Google Scholar to search the grey literature. The search was conducted by applying a multiple-term search and retrieving the search results from the search engine. The following keywords were used in the search string:

“data lifecycle” “record retention” “data ownership” OR “information ownership” “personal information” OR “personal data”

Variations of the keywords listed were used for both the Google Scholar search engine and academic databases to obtain the maximum number of relevant results.

3.1 Literature search results

A total of one hundred and sixty-three results were returned from ScienceDirect, Web of Science, Sabinet, and results are depicted in Fig. 2. The systematic literature review revealed considerable variation in the terminology used across studies. These inconsistencies posed challenges in comparing existing research as authors frequently employed divergent terms to describe similar concepts. Although the search strategy encompassed terms related to data protection and data retention, many publications instead framed their discussions around data privacy and archiving. For instance, some studies emphasised the prompt disposal of personal data upon the conclusion of the retention period, whereas others focused on the preservation of records, both addressing aspects of data retention and destruction albeit through different terminological lenses [7] [9].

3.2 Terminology Variations

There was various terminology used by researchers. When referring to personal information, some may call it personal data, personally identifiable data and others sensitive data. The search criteria covered all possible variations to find the appropriate literature for review.

- Data protection: Data that is protected efficiently and effectively [2].
- Data Privacy: The right to protect against the unwanted collection and use of personal information [24].
- Privacy Policy: A website's privacy policy advises users about policies and procedures regarding the collection, purpose of use, sharing, access to data, technologies used for data security, and disclosure of their personal information [25].
- Personally Identifiable Information (PII): There are restrictions on the length of time that organisation can store Personally Identifiable Information [21].

- Personal Information (PI): Personal information includes names, identity numbers, address information, online identifiers such as IP addresses, and, in the health research context, medical records of a patient, biometric data, and genomic data [26]. PI is also referred to as Personally Identifiable Information (PII) [3].
- Personal Data: Personal data in their example as: name, sex, phone no, address, passwords and unique identification numbers [24].
- Retention: Privacy data should be promptly disposed of upon reaching the end of the data retention period [3].
- Storage: Identifying the location where sensitive data are stored [2].
- Archiving: Archiving is referred to as record keeping [27].
- Records Management: The preservation of records and the conditions associated with preserving records is defined as retention [9].
- Sensitive Information: Patient information kept in medical practices does not only include personal details, but the nature of this may also be extremely sensitive and intimate [26].
- The location where sensitive data is stored [2].
- Special Information: Processing personal data of children that could potentially cause harm. Before processing a child's personal data, verifiable parental consent is needed [25].
- Anonymisation: Anonymization is a process through which a user can hardly ever identify a data subject [24].
- Pseudo-anonymisation: There are insufficient ways for data subjects to advise organisations to have their data deleted, pseudonymised, or encrypted [28].
- Deletion: Organisations are obligated to delete personal data unless mandated by law [4].
- De-identification: De-identification is a process whereby a person takes steps to delete all personal information that can identify a data subject in the data set [24].

3.3 Data Analysis and Selection

As illustrated in Fig. 2, 163 publications were retrieved from database searching. A total of 163 publications were screened, removing 2 duplicate publications found after analysis. Fig. 2 depicts that 0 publications were excluded from the search after applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Additionally, the abstracts or introductions on these publications were screened.

The full text of the 161 publications was reviewed to assess eligibility. 14 publications were excluded after analysing the relevance to this study. A total of 147 publications met the inclusion criteria set out for this study.

4 Discussion

Given the extensive data collection and processing within the digital economy, it is crucial for data controllers and processors to have a clear understanding of which data

sets belong to each category [29]. This clarity is essential for organisations to efficiently plan their compliance expenses and assist regulatory agencies to conduct their oversight consistently and efficiently [30]. The results identified in the literature have been grouped into seven factor groups. The factors have been systematically mapped to identify the indicators necessary for ensuring adherence to the recommended data retention and destruction guidelines, which include:

- Factor 1: Protection and privacy [3][2][31][9][11][14]
- Factor 2: Data and Information Ownership [28][3][8][16][32]
- Factor 3: Policy Development [8] [9][22]
- Factor 4: Data Classification [2][33]
- Factor 5: Data and Information inventory [11][12]
- Factor 6: Retention Schedule [13]
- Factor 7: Destruction Methods [8]

4.1 Factor 1: Protection and Privacy

Data protection and privacy are the overarching functions that guide the owners towards fulfilling the necessary functions needed for the successful execution of a retention and destruction model. Security measures are essential to prevent data leakage and should include restricted access control measures and encryption of specific data fields [4]. Privacy pertains to the methods by which personal data is collected from data subjects, as well as the processes through which it is stored, utilised, and managed [34]. Privacy practices are typically outlined in an organisation's privacy policy, which must be accessible to data subjects to ensure transparency and compliance with data protection regulations [24].

Indicators for this factor include 1.1) Privacy Policy [31][2] [9], 1.2) Information Security Policy [28][11], 1.3) Identity and Access Management [35][14] and 1.4) Data Governance [11][32].

4.2 Factor 2: Data and Information Ownership

Organisations must know what records they have created or received and how to prioritise the task of keeping them and more importantly, who is responsible for ensuring retention and destruction [27]. Ownership of retention and destruction must be established for decision-making processes and must be assigned to members that can be held accountable.

Indicators for this factor include 2.1) Data ownership [8][22] and 2.2) Data stewardship [14][16].

4.3 Factor 3: Policy Development

The formulation of policies requires the development of clear and comprehensive guidelines that govern the appropriate handling, use and protection of data [14]. An

essential component of effective policy development is the involvement of stakeholders from multiple departments to ensure alignment with organisational needs and practical feasibility [14].

Indicators for this factor include 3.1) Non-compliance procedures [5][14][22] and 3.2) Policy reviews [1][14][34].

4.4 Factor 4: Data Classification

Due to the extensive data collection and processing within the current digital landscape, it is crucial for data controllers and processors to have a clear understanding of which data sets belong to each category [29]. In support of data security initiatives, data classification has received the bulk of attention and has been hailed by all walks of life [13].

Indicators for this factor include 4.1) Data Classification Policy [13][22][36].

4.5 Factor 5: Data/Information Inventory

The collected data may contain sensitive information and therefore, it is imperative to apply effective preventive and detective methods for the retention of data. A data/information inventory is a clear method to display the classification of the data, the data's location, data ownership and where to access the retention schedule.

Indicators for this factor include 5.1) Implementation and review of a Data Catalogue [37][38].

4.6 Factor 6: Retention Schedule

Retained or stored data should be protected from multiple threats by combining physical security techniques and data protection technologies [14]. In cases where it is not completely reliable, such as in the cloud, data integrity and confidentiality must be maintained through privacy-preserving technologies [3]. A retention schedule is a mechanism used to determine when a retention period has concluded and should specify the appropriate methodology or techniques for data destruction.

Indicators for this factor include implementation of a 6.1) Data retention schedule [14][32][38] and 6.2) Triggers for destruction [27][37].

4.7 Factor 7: Destruction Methods

One method of destroying data can be seen as de-identification of a data subject. It should not be possible for an individual to manipulate the data to identify a data subject [24]. This includes actions such as altering or arranging columns and/or data or modifying the attributes or permissions of a file to uncover information that could identify a data subject.

Indicators for this factor include 7.1) Data Anonymisation [31][6][33] [39], 7.2) De-Identification [24][26][40] and 7.3) Deletion [8].

4.8 Proposed Framework

The various gaps highlighted in the literature have been visually represented by the author in the form of a conceptual retention and destruction model. The factors and indicators are organised within the model to guide activities aimed at ensuring compliance with data retention and destruction requirements. The indicators are outlined alongside each factor as depicted in Fig.3.

The factors are represented by five pillars that display policy development, data classification, data or information inventory, retention schedule and destruction methods. The pillars refer to the functions that are needed for effective retention and destruction standards and procedures. The foundational factor these pillars rest on is the ownership of data and information. The factors of protection and privacy serve as a governance function to oversee the effective implementation of the retention and destruction framework.

The indicators will provide structured guidance within each factor, to assist the organisation in determining its current maturity level. The indicators are designed to offer recommendations for strengthening maturity levels to establish a robust framework for ensuring compliance with data retention and destruction requirements.

Fig. 3. Retention and Destruction Model, created by the author.

Fig. 3 illustrates the factors and indicators influencing data retention and destruction as identified in this systematic literature review.

5 Conclusion

Data retention focuses on the safekeeping and maintenance of organisational information for the intended period and intended purpose and thereafter discarding it safely and securely. Ownership for retention and destruction must be established for decision-making processes and must be assigned to members who can be held accountable. To reiterate, it is crucial for data controllers and processors to have a clear understanding of which data sets belong to each category [26]. As mentioned, a decision must be made about the destruction of data and even during the destruction phase of the lifecycle data security and integrity must be maintained with complete certainty that no one else possesses additional knowledge that could potentially lead to re-identification [22].

Further research is necessary to fully understand the legal and technical implications of data anonymisation, considering new legislation, court decisions, and developing best practices [22]. Staying informed and compliant with these standards will help cultivate a data-driven environment that respects privacy, protects personal information and encourages responsible data retention.

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